

Overcoming barriers to COVID-19 vaccination

Rooted NWA and UAMS Community Health and Research

UAMS and Rooted NWA worked with the Hispanic community in Northwest Arkansas to determine how to create a better path toward COVID-19 vaccination together.

Getting vaccinated

Barriers

Transportation to vaccine clinics can be difficult, and **public transportation is not always available in Northwest Arkansas.**

Instructions on where to go to get the vaccine are **not always specific.** Vaccine clinics can be hard to locate within a large business or area.

It can be hard to make an appointment for those who have trouble with the phone or Internet, or who do not speak English.

Many people lack insurance and avoid vaccination due to **cost concerns.**

Solutions

We offer mobile vaccine **where the community lives** (i.e., St. Raphael's Catholic Church, St. Vincent de Paul Catholic Church).

Transportation assistance has been provided through **United Way/211** and through **partnering organizations.**

We provide **clear, in-language instruction** on how to get to vaccine events, and offer flyers for each of our events in Spanish.

Walk-ups are encouraged at all of our vaccine sites. We have also made registration for events easier, and have hired members of the community to help people get through the entire vaccination process.

We clearly communicate that COVID-19 vaccines **cost nothing to the patient**, and have **embedded community health workers** to help patients navigate the healthcare system.

If a patient is interested in obtaining health insurance, or has questions regarding other areas of healthcare, **our community health workers are available to help.**

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Getting the correct information

Barriers

Language barriers make getting the vaccination or information about the vaccine very difficult.

Vaccine events may not be equipped with staff who speak Spanish, so Spanish-speaking patients **are unable to have questions answered** in a way that is understandable to them.

Technical or academic language about the vaccine can be hard to understand. Vaccine information should be delivered **at a more basic level**.

Solutions

Spanish-speaking community health workers have been hired to help the Hispanic community obtain accurate information about the COVID-19 vaccine and local vaccine events.

We provide information in Spanish at **every part of the vaccine process**, and in language that is easily understood:

- Flyers, educational materials and social media posts **are all created in Spanish** and shared with community partners
- Launched digital ad campaigns and with **La Prensa, La Zeta, Pandora & Spotify** to reach Hispanic populations
- Spanish-speaking staff and community health workers are on-hand at every vaccine event to **translate** and **explain information**

We utilize local media and social media to distribute information that is in-language and at an appropriate literacy level so Spanish-speaking community members have **constant access to accurate information**.

Immigration status & documentation

Barriers

Many people are afraid that vaccination sites may be a way to identify undocumented immigrants and **send them back to their countries**.

Many are **afraid to provide personal information** at vaccination sites.

Solutions

We communicate in advertisements and flyers for our vaccine events that proof of citizenship or legal status, a Social Security number, and insurance are **not required for vaccination**.

While we ask for a Social Security number at the UAMS drive-thru, **we do not require one be given to receive vaccination**.